

The Via Egnatia in Late Antiquity and Beyond an analysis of scholarship on the route, and some suggestions for future historical enquiry

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ABSTRACT

For over a thousand years through Late Antiquity and the Byzantine Era, the Via Egnatia was the major Roman route from Dyrrachium or Apollonia to Constantinople. Despite this, there have been few attempts to produce a complete study of the route, and the studies that do exist are not as substantial as those that have been published for other significant Roman roads. This paper will demonstrate the shortcomings of recent scholarship on the Via Egnatia, and also show that numismatic and archaeological evidence, along with textual sources, can help to produce an up-to-date and complete study.

Keywords: Via Egnatia, Late antiquity.

The Via Egnatia was originally constructed under the orders of the prefect Egnatius after the Roman conquest of Greece in 146 BCE. On completion, the route commenced from Apollonia or Dyrrachium, and traversed the provinces of Illyricum, Macedonia, and Thrace en route to Constantinople; the route covered several hundred miles and passed important cities along the way. A study by Lolos demonstrated the continued importance of the route throughout the Roman era into Late Antiquity, charting several repair works undertaken by emperors from Trajan (r.98 - 117 CE) in the second century CE to Justinian (r.527 - 565 CE) in the sixth century CE. My discussion, however, only briefly touched on how these Christian groups appropriated the Biblical locations of Sinai from Judaism. Just as Christians believed that their faith superseded the Jews regarding their scriptures, they also took over holy sites, such as Mount Sinai, and the memory and veneration of holy figures such as Moses.¹ Though late antique and earlier Judaism did not identify a specific location as “Mount Sinai” and there was no tradition of Jewish pilgrimage to the Sinai, Christians did have to contend with the Jewish conception of the Sinai in the Exodus account.

However, although Lolos’s study ends with Justinian, the route of the Via Egnatia must have survived, as it is one of the major land routes taken by the First Crusade en route to Constantinople. The gap between Lolos’s study and the First Crusade can be attributed to the lack of direct mentions of the Via Egnatia in the primary sources covering the era after the reign of Justinian. The primary Byzantine sources, such as Theophanes’s Chronicle covering the seventh and eighth centuries, and Skylitzes’s Synopsis of Byzantine History, which covers the ninth to eleventh centuries, do not make direct reference to the Via Egnatia. Some cities that existed along the route of the Via Egnatia are mentioned, but without placing them in the

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Figure 2. Major Roman Roads in Southeast Europe. The Via Egnatia Originates at either Dyrrachium or Apollonia (5 and 6 respectively) and runs to Constantinople (1).^v

As one can see, the network of Roman roads in Italy in the map in Figure one above is far more detailed than the map of Southeast Europe in Figure two. Part of the problem is undoubtedly geographical; one can see the elevation scale on Haldon's map in Figure one above, which demonstrates that there are numerous mountain ranges that make traversing Southeast Europe by road difficult. Another problem is the modern political situation in Southeast Europe. The Via Egnatia traversed the Roman provinces of Illyricum, Macedonia, and Thrace, but this constitutes what is now Albania, the Republic of North Macedonia, Greece, and Turkey.

Despite the factors that would hinder a study, much has been produced in order that a detailed exploration of life along the route of Via Egnatia in Late Antiquity and beyond can take place. By focusing on three key areas: Byzantine Control, Economic Activity, and Maintenance of the route of the Via Egnatia, such a project would be able to improve an understanding of the continuity and survival of the major Roman route through Southeast Europe. An examination of some of the scholarship on these aspects shall now take place, before concluding with some questions a detailed study would help to answer. It should be noted at this point that a complete study for another major Byzantine route, the Via Militaris, has recently been completed. As this work uses not only historical sources but also

archaeological and numismatic evidence, then our attention should also be drawn to these areas in a study of the Via Egnatia, and shall therefore be included in the analysis.^{vi}

Control in the period

The typical narrative of Byzantine control of Southeast Europe during Late Antiquity is that the region was overrun by the Slavs and Avars during the sixth and seventh centuries. This comes from the major textual sources such as Theophanes's *Chronicle*, and Constantine VII's *De Administrando Imperio*.^{vii} This line of thought was predominant in early twentieth-century scholarship, and is still the position of popular histories today; an example of the extent of Byzantine control (and by extension, loss of control) of the area south of the Danube River, which had been a frontier of the Roman Empire, is shown in Haldon's map in figure three below.^{viii}

Map III The empire in c. A.D. 650-700: the process of devastation

Figure 3. A typical depiction of the typically described loss of Byzantine control of the provinces of Illyricum, Macedonia, and Thrace.^{ix}

However, the last half-century has seen a significant amount of writing arguing against a complete overrun of the region by the Sklavenes and Bulgars during the sixth and seventh centuries. This can be seen in the continued survival of Thessalonica, and some other cities along the route of the Via Egnatia.^x Reading the sources, it can also be seen that the various tribes who settled Southeast Europe must have maintained a nominal submission to the Emperor, attested to by the peaceful resettlement policies of Emperors such as Constans II (r.642 - 668 CE) and Justinian II (in his first reign between 685 and 695 CE) in the seventh century.^{xi} It should also be pointed out that both Theophanes's *Chronicle* was written more than two centuries on from the events that are described in it, and as such, the compilation in of the accounts leads to occasional inaccuracies.^{xii} Constantine VII's *De Administrando Imperio* also suggests that the peoples who settled in Southeast Europe during the seventh century were seeking the protection of the Emperor Heraclius (r. 610 - 641 CE).^{xiii} This statement can be challenged by both sides, as it is also written over three centuries after the events that it

describes, and may therefore be understating the way in which the tribes had settled in Southeast Europe. However, at face value, it suggests a peaceful settlement, and submission to the Emperor, by the tribes, which may explain the ease with which some of these resettlements by Emperors reigning after Heraclius took place.

Modern evidence may also help to challenge the theory that almost the entirety of Illyricum, Macedonia, and Thrace were lost, as scholars have compiled lists of people who are known to have existed during Late Antiquity.^{xiv} Charting the numbers of people living in settlements along the Via Egnatia may help to determine who lived in these settlements, whether they identified as Roman (or Byzantine) and whether they had moved or relocated during the sixth and seventh centuries. Whilst such a study can only ever account for a tiny fraction of all the people that existed at that time, the presence of an elite at a time when the Eastern Roman Empire is often portrayed as on the verge of collapse would certainly challenge this view.^{xv}

Another method of challenging the overrun of Southeast Europe by the Sklavenes and Bulgars is to examine the presence of the church in the region. Until their conversions to Christianity, the Sklavenes and Bulgars perceived to have overrun Southeast Europe during the seventh and eighth centuries are depicted as pagans, in opposition to the Christian Romans. During this period, there were several ecumenical councils attended by bishops from across the Eastern Roman Empire. The lists of attendees could also therefore be used to chart Imperial control of Southeast Europe, as cities with their own bishops may still have been under Byzantine control. Herrin has recently used these lists to highlight the importance of the Bishops of Ravenna at these Ecumenical Councils, but the Bishop of Ravenna ranks lower than his counterpart in Thessalonica.^{xvi} Whilst Thessalonica was never taken by the Slavs, the lists of attendees at the councils may show that it was not alone in remaining under Byzantine control during Late Antiquity. Regarding the Via Egnatia, the presence of bishops from the cities along it would help to determine how much of the route was, or was not, lost during the period.

A combination of sources and archaeology can be used to chart fortifications and the emergence of *Thema* in the eighth and ninth century, and paint a clearer picture of direct Byzantine control of the route of the Via Egnatia. Studies of the fortifications in Byzantine Macedonia and Thrace have revealed that fortifications, originally attributed to the Empress Irene by Theophanes's *Chronicle*, may in fact have been constructed earlier in the eighth century during the reigns of her predecessors, Constantine V and Leo III.^{xvii} If true, then Byzantine control of the region of Thrace during the eighth century may have been stronger than previously thought, perhaps also attested by the creation of the *Thema* of Thrace in the late seventh century.^{xviii} The designations of *Thema* along the Via Egnatia have been charted by Treadgold, which include several *Thema* created in the eighth and ninth century.^{xix} Although Treadgold does not directly reference the Via Egnatia in his study of the *Byzantine Revival* that took place during this period, the creation of *Thema* in Dyrrachium, Thrace, Macedonia, and Thessalonica certainly speaks of Byzantine control along the vast majority of the route of the Via Egnatia, which is displayed in the map in figure four below.^{xx}

Economic Activity in the Period

The Via Egnatia connected several important cities along its route, including Ohrid, Heraclea Lyncestis, Thessalonica, and Traianoupolis; these cities experienced mixed fortunes during Late Antiquity and into the Byzantine Era beyond.^{xxiv} The traditional view from twentieth-century scholarship was that urban life, including in the cities along the Via Egnatia, declined, or suffered a catastrophic fate during the sixth and seventh centuries; this is linked to the loss of Byzantine control of Southeast Europe depicted in the textual sources mentioned above.^{xxv} However, later twentieth and early twenty-first-century scholarship has challenged this position; a brief summary of the challenges posed by the traditional model of decline was recently charted by Magdalino.^{xxvi}

As stated above in the chapter on control, one has to consider that the primary sources that early twentieth-century scholars are referencing were often written long after the event, or to justify the actions of an emperor. Theophanes's *Chronicle* was written in the early ninth century and is therefore brief in its recounting of the two centuries it covers, particularly the mid-seventh century where a whole year is often summarised in as little as one sentence.^{xxvii} Similarly, the *Chronicon Paschale* of the seventh century is often used to portray the villainous deeds of Emperor Phokas (r.602 - 610 CE) to justify the civil war caused by his successor Heraclius and paint Heraclius as the savior of the Eastern Roman Empire during the Persian wars between 602-628 CE.^{xxviii} As a result of the biases of these source texts, neither Theophanes nor the *Chronicon Paschale* goes into great detail about economic activity in the cities, save from the occasional event such as the trade fair at Ephesus that is mentioned in Theophanes's *Chronicle*.^{xxix}

With the primary sources being of limited use, other methods of historical inquiry must be used to provide evidence of decline or transformation in urban life during Late Antiquity. An often-cited argument for the economic decline was the cessation of the use of silver and bronze coinage as part of a monetized economy.^{xxx} This view was initially challenged by Ostrogorsky in the mid-twentieth century, citing that although the use of silver and bronze coins ceased, the use of gold coins increased, implying that there was money amongst the elite of Byzantine society.^{xxxi}

The cessation of bronze and copper coins has been linked by Hendy to the loss of the mints during the Slavic, Avar, and Persian invasions of the early seventh century.^{xxxii} What is not mentioned by Hendy is the loss of several mines, which would have hindered coin production, as there was nothing to mint the coins with.^{xxxiii} If the means to produce the coins were non-existent, then this would have contributed to the loss of a monetized economy. However, goods were still being shipped around the eastern Mediterranean, and so a bartering economy must have continued to exist, a concept that shall now be explored.

An argument for the decline of economic activity points to the end of total Roman control of the Mediterranean causing the long-established trading networks to cease, or be substantially reduced.^{xxxiv} However, the diagram below shows Vroom's charting of the extent of ceramic distribution through the coastal town of Butrint in the Eastern Mediterranean during the Early and Middle Byzantine periods, which shows that although its reach was diminished, trade across the Mediterranean was still ongoing and active after the disruptions of the seventh century.

Figure 5. The extent of the distribution of ceramics from or through Butrint in the Early and Middle Byzantine periods. ^{xxxv}

Unfortunately, in her study of the Mediterranean trade network emanating from Butrint, Vroom has highlighted a large quantity of locally produced pottery but does not mention how this locally produced pottery made its way to Butrint.^{xxxvi} The focus on the extent of items being traded from Butrint overlooks the smaller overland trade within the hinterlands of Butrint, which would have contributed to the economic activity there.

In the context of the Via Egnatia, the importance of Dyrrachium, Thessalonica, and Constantinople as centers of commercial activity is known, so a study of the Via Egnatia can determine how far inland valuable items were traded along the route from the coastal port towns. By combining the material evidence from archaeology with the sources to demonstrate the economic activity taking place, a much clearer picture of the transformation of cities along the Via Egnatia can substantially aid a study of the route.

More can still be done to create a bigger picture of economic activity in Late Antiquity, however. Modern scholarship has shown that coins are still present in Southeast Europe during the late sixth century, and the route of the Via Egnatia can often be traced, even though it is not the primary focus of the study. Gandila, for example, has covered the use of the *folles* for the region up to the Danube, but within the map that he has produced, which is displayed in figure five below, one can make out the route of the Via Egnatia.

Figure 6. Dispersal of 16-nummia coins across Southeast Europe. The route of the Via Egnatia can likely be traced between the square number 76 (representing a coin hoard at Thessalonica), the coin hoard (73) at Heraclea Lyncestis, the find at Pogradec (39) and the one at Dyrrachium (33).^{xxxvii}

The phenomenon of being able to trace the route of the Via Egnatia within a larger body of work is not unique to Gandila. A similar problem exists with Ciglencečki's work, which covers cities between Ravenna and Constantinople. Whilst Ciglencečki does acknowledge the cities that are on the Via Egnatia, the cities themselves are dispersed amongst a vast body of work that covers the entirety of Southeast Europe in Late Antiquity.^{xxxviii} Ciglencečki has also not acknowledged Thessalonica's presence on the Via Egnatia, in spite of its importance during this period.^{xxxix}

The examples in this chapter have highlighted the need for a study of the cities along the route of the Via Egnatia. Presently, the route of the Via Egnatia is lost amongst a larger body of work, and one has to sift through complete studies of Southeast Europe in order to find information relative to the route. A new study with attention paid specifically to the cities along the Via Egnatia would illuminate any changes in economic activity that happened along the route, and how these fitted into the broader patterns of trade and exchange that the works mentioned in this chapter have argued. With Control and Economic Activity examined the paper shall now focus on the Maintenance of the Via Egnatia.

Maintenance in the Period

As the route of the Via Egnatia remained in use for almost a millennium, it must have been maintained, but how did this happen? Lolos's study tracked the history of the repairs of the Via Egnatia by using textual sources, so was able to chart the improvements made to cities along the route of the Via Egnatia by Anastasius (r.491 - 518 CE) and Justinian in the early sixth century.^{xi} Lolos also mentions an inscription found at Traianoupolis, which says that the city assumed responsibility for the upkeep of the Via Egnatia.^{xii} However, this inscription is dated to 202 CE, so can we be sure that this was still the case during Late Antiquity and beyond? The likelihood of Traianoupolis being responsible for the maintenance of the Via Egnatia beyond the Classical Era may also be challenged by the Byzantine control of the route of the Via Egnatia. The map in figure three by Haldon on page six above highlights this issue. If Haldon's assumption of the territory controlled by the Eastern Roman Empire circa 640 CE is correct, then a substantial proportion of the Via Egnatia between Thessalonica and Dyrrachium is out of Imperial control at the time, and Byzantine maintenance would have been highly unlikely in the seventh and eighth centuries. Lolos's conclusions about Traianoupolis may therefore be correct for the Classical Era, but there must have been a different method of maintenance taking place in the later seventh and eighth centuries.

Throughout Roman history, a succession of emperors would redevelop the city of their birth, the most relevant example for the Via Egnatia in Late Antiquity being Anastasius's renovation of Dyrrachium in the early sixth century.^{xiii} These projects may also have included renovations of the roads that passed through the cities along the Via Egnatia. Additionally, Procopius credits Justinian with the renovation of the Via Egnatia close to the city of Rhegium in *On Buildings*, so it appears that Traianoupolis would not be solely responsible for the upkeep of the entire Via Egnatia by the sixth century.^{xiii} However, scholarship is often wary of Procopius, as he also tells us in his *Secret History* that Justinian left the roads to fall into decline during his reign, so a study of the maintenance of the Via Egnatia can help our understanding of Procopius's writings.^{xiv} There are those such as Cameron, for example, who dismiss *On Buildings* as a panegyric to Emperor Justinian's projects.^{xv} As there are arguments for both sides of the debate on Procopius, a study on the Via Egnatia, and the cities along the route, can aid one side of this debate.

Returning to the maintenance of the Via Egnatia, the bridge that formed part of Justinian's repairs to the Via Egnatia was said to have been repaired by Basil I in the ninth century, which strongly implies a continuation of the policy of Emperors to maintain the route of the Via Egnatia.^{xvi} Something that could also aid a study of the maintenance of the Via Egnatia is to use epigraphic evidence, in a way similar to Lolos's study highlighting the maintenance of the Via Egnatia near Traianoupolis. The compendium of milestones along the Via Egnatia by Collart can perhaps aid a study of maintenance of the route, should such maintenance have been recorded at the milestones.^{xvii} Similarly, should archaeology attest to the continued presence of waystations along the route of the Via Egnatia, then any maintenance of the waystations may also help to determine the maintenance of the route.

Conclusions, what more can be uncovered?

The survival of key Roman infrastructure from the Classical Era clearly played a part in the transition to Late Antiquity. Thanks to the work of scholars such as Pickett, our understanding of water infrastructure has improved vastly in the last decade, whilst roads, especially the Via Egnatia, have fallen behind in comparison.^{xviii} This comes in spite of the road networks having been highlighted as a factor in the continued Economic Activity in Apulia during the sixth to tenth centuries by Arthur.^{xlix}

As we have seen, past studies of the route of the Via Egnatia have often left something to be desired. They have either focused on a short section in detail, or they have been very general

across the entirety of the route of the Via Egnatia. Both methods have merits, but also their drawbacks. A detailed short study can tell us a great deal about a limited part of the route, whereas a limited study of the entire route can tell us about one or possibly two aspects of life along the Via Egnatia.

In this short breakdown of what does exist, it is apparent that, in light of recent scholarship, the traditional view of life in the seventh and eighth centuries regressing to a “Dark Age” after Justinian needs to be challenged.ⁱ By using numismatics, epigraphy, and archaeology along with the textual sources, a complete work that furthers understanding of what was occurring along the Via Egnatia can be undertaken.

The last major attempt to study the route was undertaken by Fasolo in 2003, and received unfavorably due to the overwhelming amount of (sometimes repeated) information; the review also highlighted the nature of the work, describing it as that of a “learned amateur, rather than a professional scholar.”ⁱⁱ Since Fasolo’s work, a complete study of the Via Militaris, one of the other major Roman routes in medieval Thrace and Bulgaria, was completed by Lanarch in 2016; a study which covers Late Antiquity and beyond into the Middle Ages.ⁱⁱⁱ However, Lanarch’s chapter on the roads in Southeast Europe only mentions the Via Egnatia once in a comment about Raideostos.ⁱⁱⁱⁱ This comes in spite of a heavy focus on Thessalonica, one of the most prominent cities along the route, during the chapter.^{lv} There have also been recent publications on the regions Macedonia and Eastern Thrace, so although one would have to sift through volumes of data to find places along the Via Egnatia, there is, even more, to draw upon than before.^{lv}

Despite the paper demonstrating the importance, and likely use of, the Via Egnatia beyond the Classical Era, there are some who doubt that the route did retain its purpose. Lolos says that the Via Egnatia dwindled in importance in Late Antiquity because it was no longer the major through route between Italy and Constantinople, largely based on an *Iteneria* that records a journey through Southeast Europe via Hadrianoupolis and Phillippopolis instead of along the Via Egnatia.^{lvi} McCormick goes further and says that overland travel ceased in Late Antiquity due to the Slavic invasions of Southeast Europe discussed above.^{lvii} This is based on the lists of journeys that are known, rather than the ones that aren’t.^{lviii} Although important dignitaries may no longer have traveled on the Via Egnatia, for the ordinary person the route should have played an important role in everyday life. However, a study that would confirm this, such as how far inland luxury goods and items traveled inland from the Via Egnatia’s port towns, which would prove a continued use of the route, is so far lacking.^{lix}

Whilst, therefore, much is known about the Via Egnatia, a complete study would help to tackle many of the issues that this paper has raised. Communities continued to exist along, and use, the route of the Via Egnatia. How they were able to do so, and their reasons to use it, be they for military or civilian purposes, is a question that needs answering. It is high time that more is known about how these communities survived during Late Antiquity and the Byzantine Middle Ages.

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ⁱ The literature on this topic is extensive and cannot be fully described here. See Dunn 2000, pp. 248-254; Hirshman 1996; Mac Cormack, S. 1990, pp. 7-40.

ⁱⁱ Ashby and Fell 1921, p. 125-190.

ⁱⁱⁱ Hammond 1974, p. 185-194 on the Western Via Egnatia; Fasolo 2009, p. 601-612 covering the Republic of Macedonia.

^{iv} Christie 2006, p. 403.

^v Haldon 1999, 55.

^{vi} Lanarch 2016, p. 3.

- vii Theophanes, *Chronicle*. Trans Turtledove, p. 12; Constantine VII, *De Administrando Imperio*. Trans Jenkins. Chapters 31-36.
- viii Jones 1966, p. 119-120; Stephenson 2019, p. 275-329.
- ix Haldon 1990, p. 65.
- x Ciglencčki 2023, p. 92.
- xi Theophanes, *Chronicle*. Trans Turtledove, p. 46, 62
- xii *Ibid*, p. 94.
- xiii Constantine VII, *De Administrando Imperio*. Trans. Jenkins. Books 31-36
- xiv Jones, Martindale and Morris 1971, Vols 1-3.
- xv Wickham 2005, p. 353
- xvi Herrin 2020, p. 269.
- xvii Dunn 1997, p. 145.
- xviii Treadgold 1997, p. 329.
- xix Treadgold 1988, p. 330-386.
- xx Treadgold 1988, p. 350.
- xxi Treadgold 1988, p. 336.
- xxii Magdalino 2003, p. 119.
- xxiii Theophanes *Chronicle*. Trans. Turtledove, p. 55-58.
- xxiv Lolos 2007, p. 274-276.
- xxv Jones 1966, p. 119-120; Mango 1980, p. 66-73.
- xxvi Magdalino 2016, p. 45-62.
- xxvii Theophanes *Chronicle*. Trans. Turtledove, p. 42, for example.
- xxviii Chronicon Pashcale. Trans. Whitby and Whitby, p. 145-146.
- xxix Theophanes *Chronicle*. Trans. Turtledove, p. 152
- xxx Ward-Perkins 2005, p. 114-115.
- xxxi Ostrogorsky 1957, p. 51.
- xxxii Hendy 1985, p. 418, for example.
- xxxiii Laiou and Morrison 2007, p. 63-64.
- xxxiv Wickham 2005, p. 355.
- xxxv Vroom 2021, p. 71.
- xxxvi Vroom 2021, p. 50.
- xxxvii Gandila 2018, p. 433.
- xxxviii Ciglencčki 2023, p. 19-149.
- xxxix Ciglencčki 2023, p. 89-91.
- xl Lolos 2007, p. 279.
- xli *Ibid*, p. 279.
- xlii Nicks 1998, p. 264.
- xliii Procopius, *De Aedificiis* 4.8.
- xliv Procopius, *Secret History*. 26
- xlv Cameron 1993, p. 118.
- xlvi Avramea in Laiou 2007, p. 71.
- xlvii Collart 1976, p. 76-100.
- xlviii Pickett 2015, p. 425-468.

- ^{xlix} Arthur 2010, p. 552.
^l Haldon 1990, p. 1.
^{li} Fasolo 2003; Bucher 2003 for the review.
^{lii} Lanarch 2016, p. 131-263.
^{liii} *Ibid*, p. 114.
^{liv} *Ibid*, p. 99-124.
^{lv} Kulzer 2008; Soustal et. al 2022.
^{lvi} Lolos 2007, p. 275.
^{lvii} McCormick 2002, p. 67-77.
^{lviii} *Ibid*, p. 799-810.
^{lix} Lolos 2007, p. 280.

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